

OSCILLATING SPECTRA ASSOCIATED TO CERTAIN SEQUENCES

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ABSTRACT. Identities originating in the theory of symmetric functions express members of arithmetic sequences as determinants. In this setting we studied numerically sequences $\{a(n)\}_{n \geq 1}$ derived from the Fourier expansions of cusp forms. We observed that, within the range of our observations, in certain cases the spectra of matrices we attached to these sequences exhibit oscillatory behavior. We collect data on this behavior in some other sequences. We propose that sequences exhibiting oscillatory behavior may form vector spaces. We initiate testing of this proposal.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Identities ([M], Lemmas 2.1 and 2.2 below) originating in the theory of symmetric functions express members of arithmetic sequences $\{h_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ with $h_0 = 1$ as $h_n = |J_{h,n}|/n!$ for particular matrices $J_{h,n}$ where $|\cdot|$ is the determinant. (In the sequel, we denote the cardinality of a set S as $\#S$.)

Let μ_n stand for the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues of $J_{h,n}$. We plotted the data sets $\{(n, \mu_n)\}_n$. After a procedure we will call *deformation* by a number c , such plots for the deformed matrix $J_{h,n}^{(c)}$ sometimes appear to oscillate in a nearly periodic fashion with n ; addressing the question of when is part of our project.

We saw the oscillatory behavior in, for example, the sequence $\{h_n\}_{n \geq 0} = \{\lambda_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ where $\lambda_0 = 1, \lambda_n = \tau(p_n)$ for positive integers n , where tau is Ramanujan's function, and where p_n denotes the n^{th} prime number. D. H. Lehmer showed [Le47] that, if tau has any zeros, the smallest has the form λ_{n^*} for some n^* . In our setup, this would mean that the spectrum of J_{λ,n^*} contains zero. This motivated our project.

The μ_n data for the spectra of undeformed J_{λ,n^*} are not encouraging. (They are plotted for an initial segment of $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ in Figure 7.) The regularizing effect of deforming these matrices, however, is dramatic. (See Figures 2, 3, and 4.) The appearance of very nearly regular behavior in *some* deformed matrices raises the prospect that their spectra might be helpful.

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But we have not found a way to guarantee, for example, that the spectrum of J_{λ,n^*} would be zero-free if $J_{\lambda,n^*}^{(c)}$ was zero-free. That is also a part of our project.

We saw similar oscillatory behavior in sequences of Fourier coefficients of newforms coming from elliptic curves listed in Cremona’s database, and in other cusp forms coming from spaces of higher weight and larger dimension, for which the vanishing of coefficients is not an issue—it is common. We also collected data on the oscillatory behavior of some simpler sequences that do not come from modular forms.

We propose that families of sequences exhibiting oscillatory behavior may have algebraic structure, and we initiate tests of this proposal. We relied on the LLM “Claude” [Anthropic2026] to write sophisticated signal analysis code because this task is not within our competence. The code is in our repository [Bre25] under the title “`version_11.py`”. A guide by Claude to the interpretation of the reports generated by this code is also stored there under the title “`v9_11_interpretation_guide.pdf`”.

Because the more interesting waveforms in our plots evolve towards oscillatory behavior only for large-enough n , we had Claude write version 11 of its code to segment the data at natural phase transitions using a package called `rupture` and to analyze only the part of the data with n so large that the pairs (n, μ_n) belong to the final segment.

The term “oscillate” as it is used in this article remains undefined. We rely on our own visual impressions to classify our data sets as oscillating or non-oscillating, especially when we are testing various hypotheses about pair data for the sequences h . Claude’s version 11 code evaluates the pair data according to several objective criteria that may become part of such a definition, but version 11 does not offer a binary verdict on oscillation.

We say that a numerical sequence $\{h_n\}_{n=0,1,\dots}$ with $h_0 = 1$ is *h-coherent* if the pairs (n, μ_n) for h oscillate. We also say that an arbitrary sequence $\{f_n\}$ of polynomials over \mathbb{Q} is *f-coherent* if (a) it is the zero-sequence or if (b) the minimum moduli among the roots of the $\{f_n\}_{n=1,2,\dots}$ oscillate. These are different ideas. The property of *f-coherence* does not require the f_n to be characteristic polynomials of matrices, but the *h-coherence* of a sequence h comes down to the *f-coherence* of a list of characteristic polynomials $\chi(J_{h,n})$.

We write V_f for the set of *f-coherent* sequences $\{f_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ and denote as V_h the set of sequences $\{h_n\}_{n > 0}$ such that $\{1, h_1, h_2, \dots\}$ is *h-coherent*. set. We exclude h_0 because we want to speculate that V_f and V_h are closed under addition, with sums taken term by term and assembled into sequences, but sequences h are studied using the lemmas in the next section that apply only to sequences such that $h_0 = 1$. Obviously, closure of V_f under multiplication by a complex number is automatic, so it becomes a vector space over \mathbb{C} if it is additively closed. The situation for V_h in this regard is less clear, because we do not know whether it is closed under multiplication by scalars. At the

time of the present draft, the scope of our tests of additive closure of V_f and V_h is limited, but we have not found counterexamples.

Here are several questions that will not be addressed in the present article. Theorem 2.3 (below) enforces various relations among the coefficients of the characteristic polynomial of a J matrix. (For example, it must have leading term 1.) Let us say that f -coherent sequences of characteristic polynomials of J matrices are J -coherent. We cannot say, at present, whether our tests of V_f for additive closure are biased by the circumstance that the sequences of f -coherent polynomials we have for testing are mainly J -coherent. Also, obviously (because our tests examine finite data sets) we do not even know that V_f and V_h are non-empty, or—if V_f is non-empty—whether it contains sequences that are not J -coherent. If it happens that V_f or V_h is a vector space, one might also ask whether one of both of them is a metric space, a Banach space, or a Hilbert space under appropriate norms, and then, whether one or the other is open, closed, or neither in some nice ambient space.

2. LEMMAS

These lemmas appear, for example, in MacDonald’s book [M], but the proofs are not easy to locate; in fact, we have not located them. Home-made proofs of these statements are stored in our repository [Bre25]¹.

Lemma 2.1. *The equations below are equivalent. (We will refer to both of them as equation (D) in the sequel.) Let $h_0 = 1$ and*

$$(D1) \quad nh_n = \sum_{r=1}^n j_r h_{n-r}$$

for $n \geq 1$. With $H(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} h_n t^n$ and $J(t) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} j_r t^r$,

$$(D2) \quad t \frac{d}{dt} H(t) = H(t)J(t).$$

With f_0 possibly defined as equal to one, let \bar{f} denote the sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$. Let $J_n(\bar{j})$ and $H_n(\bar{h})$ be the matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -n+1 \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

¹“Lemmas for ‘Ramanujan’s function on small primes’ ”

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} h_1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 2h_2 & h_1 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ nh_n & h_{n-1} & h_{n-2} & \cdots & h_1 \end{pmatrix},$$

respectively.

Lemma 2.2. *Let $h_0 = j_1 = 1$. Equation (D) implies that*

$$(1) \quad j_n = (-1)^{n+1} |H_n(\bar{h})|.$$

and

$$(2) \quad n!h_n = |J_n(\bar{j})|$$

for $n \geq 1$.

Next we state a corollary of the following theorem in Vein and Dale's book [Vein1999].

Proposition 1. *(Vein and Dale, Theorem 4.23) Let $A_n =$*

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ a_2 & a_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n-1} & a_{n-2} & \cdots & a_1 & -(n-1) \\ a_n & a_{n-1} & \cdots & a_2 & a_1 \end{pmatrix}^T,$$

where the T operator is matrix transpose. Let $B_n(x) = |A_n - xI_n|$, so that $B_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi_{A_n}(x)$. Then

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |A_r| x^{n-r}.$$

The corollary is the following

Theorem 2.3. ² *With h and j as in the above lemmas,*

$$\chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r!h_r (-1)^r x^{n-r}.$$

Proof. Determinants are invariant under the transpose, so, setting each a_i equal to j_i in the lemmas above, the proposition can be restated in the

²Here we are merely codifying an argument shown to us by J. López-Bonilla. See also the personal communication of Petović to the author *Petović's proof* [Bre25].

following way: Let $J_n(\bar{j}) =$

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -(n-1) \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & \cdots & j_2 & j_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let $C_n(x) = |(J_n(\bar{j}) - xI_n)|$, so that $C_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x))$. By Proposition 1, $C_n(x) =$

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |J_r(\bar{j})| (-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r} =$$

(by Lemma 2.2)

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r(-x)^{n-r} = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r(-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r}.$$

Simplifying, $\chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x)) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r(-1)^r x^{n-r}$. \square

Remark 1. This result allows us to bypass the calculation of determinants, resulting in a marked speedup, when computing the polynomials χ . So far we have applied it in Figure 2B below. Its implementation is described in Remark 3 below.

Now let M be an $n \times n$ matrix over a field. For any subset $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, let $M[S, S]$ denote the submatrix of M with rows and columns indexed by S . The following proposition is well known. (For example, see equation (1.2.13) in Horn and Johnson's book [Horn2012].)

Proposition 2. *The coefficient a_k of x^k in $\chi(M)$ satisfies*

$$a_{n-k} = (-1)^k \sum_{\substack{\#S=k \\ S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}}} |M[S, S]|.$$

Remark 2. Let $h_0 = 1$ and $h_n = \tau(n)$ when n is positive. Let $\{j_n\}_{n=1, 2, \dots}$ be the sequence paired with h in equation (D1) above. Now let n be positive. Then $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(0) = 0$ if and only if $|J_n(\bar{j})| = 0$, so, by Lemma 2.2.2, $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(0) = 0$ if and only if $\tau(n) = 0$. Now if $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))$ is irreducible over the rational numbers, zero is not a root of $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(x)$ and $\tau(n) \neq 0$. A similar argument works if we consider the sequence for which $h_n = \lambda(n)$ when n is positive.

We will not focus on this kind of sufficient condition in the sequel. We mention it because it is the only such condition we know at the time of the present draft. Instead we explore a geometric phenomenon: under certain conditions, which so far we cannot crisply describe, the eigenvalues of “deformed” versions of the $\chi(J_n(x))$ (defined in the next section) appear to oscillate as point sets as n increases. We would like to gain control over

this and use it to bound the distance of these eigenvalues away from zero for certain sequences h , then to devise a version of the argument to bound the eigenvalues of the original (“undeformed”) matrices away from zero as well. This seems to be a challenging task. What we would like to do at this stage is simply to understand what it is about the $\chi(J_n(x))$ that induces the observed oscillations (when in fact they do so.) We have collected lists of these characteristic polynomials for some sequences h (Fourier coefficients of modular forms), which are available to the interested reader in data files generated in the SageMath *Jupyter* notebooks in our repository [Bre25]. We have not found a way to predict whether the relevant plots oscillate simply from characteristics of the modular forms that they come from. We speculate that first we need to learn how to make such predictions from basic features of the characteristic polynomials.

3. DEFORMATIONS

For a sequence $S = \{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$, let $S^{(c)} = \{c, x_1, x_2, \dots\}$, $J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j}) = J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})$ and $H_n^{(c)}(\bar{h}) = H_n(\overline{h^{(c)}})$. We refer to them as *deformations* of the matrices $H_n(\bar{h})$ and $J_n(\bar{j})$. We will freely abuse the notation by employing the H, h, J , and j symbols to denote objects in a way that depends on the context.

Remark 3. The most straightforward workflow to find $\chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}}))$ for a given member of a sequence $\{h_n^{(c)}\}_n$ may be (concisely) diagrammed as follows:

$$h_n \xrightarrow{(D1)} j_n \longrightarrow j_n^{(c)} \longrightarrow J_n^{(c)} \longrightarrow \chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})).$$

The code in most of the *Jupyter* notebooks cited in the index of the present draft follows this pattern, but in our recent experience the following workflow is more efficient.

$$h_n \xrightarrow{(D1)} j_n \longrightarrow j_n^{(c)} \xrightarrow{(D1)} h_n^{(c)} \xrightarrow{Th.2.3} \chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})).$$

(So far we have applied it only in a few figures.)

4. THE SEQUENCE $\{\lambda_n\}$.

We define a sequence $\overline{j_\lambda}$ by requiring $j_\lambda(n)$ and $h_n = \lambda(n)$ together to satisfy equation (D). By Lemma 2.2 (2), $\lambda(n) = |J_{\lambda,n}(\bar{j})|/n!$. Let $\Pi_n(x) = \chi(J_{\lambda,n}(\bar{j}))(x) = |xI - J_{\lambda,n}(\bar{j})|$ be the characteristic polynomial of $J_{\lambda,n}(\bar{j})$. Plots 2, 3 and 4 show the behavior of the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues of $\Pi_n^{(c)}$ ($c = 1, 2, 3$) and Π_n respectively. They are relevant to Lehmer’s question (does Ramanujan’s tau function ever vanish?) because the following statements are equivalent:

- (a) $\lambda(n) = \tau(p_n) = 0$,
- (b) $|J_{\lambda,n}(\bar{j})| = 0$, and
- (c) $\Pi_n(0) = 0$.

Remark 4. Writing³ $\Pi_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,n-k} x^{n-k}$, Theorem 2.3 gives

$$(3) \quad a_{n,n-k} = (-1)^k k! \binom{n}{k} \lambda(k).$$

Remark 5. The number of terms in the sum in Proposition 2 is $\binom{n}{k}$, so the simplest way to reconcile Proposition 2 and equation (3) is to suppose that the structural symmetries of $J_{\lambda,n}(\bar{j})$ somehow force $|J_{\lambda,n}(\bar{j})[S, S]| = (-1)^k k! \lambda(k)$ just when $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $\#S = k$. But this turns out to be too good to be true.⁴ Instead, there must be systematic cancellations coming from those symmetries. So far, we have not understood these cancellations.

Let $\chi(J_{\lambda,n}^{(c)}(\bar{j})) = \Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$ (say.) Let $E_n^{(c)}$ be the set of zeros of $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$ and let $\mu_n^{(c)} = \min_{v \in E_n^{(c)}} |v|$; then it appears that the graph of the pairs $(n, \mu_n^{(c)})$ lies on an oscillating curve for $1 \leq c \leq 3$ (see Figures 2, 3 and 4). As a control, we repeated the calculation for $h_n = \tau(p_n + 1)$ with $c = 1$. Figure 6 shows the resulting plot. It shows no oscillatory behavior for this choice of h , suggesting that the choice of prime indices *per se* was decisive, but this is false. (See Remark 6.) The deep spikes in the lower, logarithmic plot in Figure 2A suggest that the approach of the roots of $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$ to the origin may behave in a predictable way, but the details are not clear to us because (among other reasons) our data is limited. We do not know the details of the relationship of the roots of $\Pi_n(x)$ to those of the $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$, so the connection, if any, to Lehmer's question is unclear.

The lower envelope of the lower plot of logarithms of minimum moduli for each n in $\{2, 3, \dots, 400\}$ displayed in Figure 3 appear to behave regularly: the abscissas of the points on the lower envelope form a set $\{5, 9, \dots, 395\}$, which, when they are replaced by their residues modulo 4, make Table 1. The size of the blocks of equal residues are 10 for the first one and 9 for each of the others.⁵

For contrast, we reproduce in Figure 7 a plot of the minimum moduli for each n for the undeformed characteristic polynomials $\Pi_n(x)$. We have not attempted the sort of analysis we just discussed for the $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$.

We want a global-in- c understanding of the deformed plots. After prepending c to \bar{j}_λ , denoting this deformation as $\overline{j_\lambda^{(c)}}$ and once more applying equation (D1), we computed the sequence $\overline{h_\lambda^{(c)}}$ from $\overline{j_\lambda^{(c)}}$. We formed the list of pairs $(c, n! h_\lambda^{(c)}(n))$. (These are just the values of the determinants from Lemma 2.2 in this situation; but now we bypass the determinants and gain

³See 'undeformed tauprime2nov25no3.ipynb' in the repository [Bre25].

⁴See 'too good.ipynb' in [Bre25].

⁵We are using data from the lower envelope of the logarithms of the minimum moduli. (The lower plot in Figure 3.) See "tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25.ipynb" in [Bre25].

significant time savings.) We found that, within the range of our observations, these pairs interpolate a polynomial D_n (say) of degree n . For given n , we found the minimum modulus among the roots of D_n and plotted these minima against n . In the case $c \in \mathbb{Z}^{\geq 0}$, the result was the same kind of oscillating wave form that the first few individual values of c exhibit, as we see in Figure 5.⁶

5. OSCILLATORY BEHAVIOR IN NEWFORMS FROM ELLIPTIC CURVES

Because the cusp form Δ is the generating function of the multiplicative Ramanujan function, which displays oscillatory behavior in the range of our observations, we searched a source of cusp forms that are generating functions of other multiplicative functions: Cremona's database [LMFDB] of cusp forms $\sum_n a(n)q^n$ associated to elliptic curves in virtue of the Modularity Theorem. We found similar oscillatory behavior. (But see the next section for examples of oscillatory behavior coming from cusp forms the coefficient functions of which are not multiplicative.)

The forms in Cremona's database have weight two and varying levels.⁷ In the limited range of our observations, there is much variation in the oscillatory behavior, or lack of it, in deformed curves.

In contrast to the inclusion of plots of the logarithms of minimum moduli among eigenvalues associated to matrices representing Ramanujan's original tau function, we omit such plots for the curves in Cremona's database. The logarithm plots in the former situation served to demonstrate that the minima were not hitting zero, but for the Cremona database curves, they must occasionally do so, because the corresponding Fourier coefficients $a(n)$ themselves occasionally vanish.

Remark 6. Among our figures we have plots of eigenvalue minimum moduli for the sequences $h_n = a(n)$ and $h_n = a(p_n)$, but also for the sequences $h_n = a(p_n + 1)$. Our original intention was to introduce controls like the one we described above, which was meant to provide some evidence for the thesis that the $\lambda_n = \tau(p_n)$ were producing oscillations because of arithmetic characteristics of the inputs. We expected to see a pattern in which the sequences $h_n = a(p_n)$ induced oscillations among the minimal eigenvalues, and the sequences $h_n = a(p_n + 1)$ did not, but there is no such pattern. This undercuts the rationale behind our original controls for $h_n = \lambda_n$. We have carried forward all controls into this article anyway, for obvious reasons.

6. CUSP FORMS FROM SPACES OF WEIGHT EXCEEDING TWO

We have begun to test for oscillatory behavior among cusp forms belonging to spaces of weight greater than two. Some Hecke eigenforms in such

⁶See Table 7 below and notebook 'tauprime many c's 18feb26' in [Bre25]. The reader will notice that we ran the routines twice, at 64-bit and 100-bit precision. The results were indistinguishable.

⁷SageMath notebooks corresponding to Table 4 are in [Bre25].

spaces have non-rational Fourier expansions. Decimal estimates of their coefficients carry error that could explode in our calculations. To avoid this issue, we examined the sums of the eigenforms over the automorphisms of their coefficient fields that fix \mathbb{Q} (the traces.) These objects have rational expansions.

To explain this, we sketch Hecke theory up to the definition of newforms. Denoting the space of cusp forms at level N and weight k as $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$, for $f, g \in S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ the Petersson inner product is defined as $\langle f, g \rangle =$

$$\int_{\Gamma_0(N)\backslash\mathfrak{H}} f(z)\overline{g(z)}y^k \frac{dx dy}{y^2}.$$

Let $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the subspace of all linear combinations of $f(dz)$ where $f \in S_k(\Gamma_0(M))$ for some $M|N$ with $M < N$ and $d|(N/M)$. Let $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the orthogonal complement of $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with respect to the Petersson inner product. Then $S_k(\Gamma_0(N)) = S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N)) \oplus S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$.

Let T_1 be the identity operator on $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ and, for primes $p \nmid N$, let the Hecke operator T_p satisfy

$$T_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(a_{pn} + p^{k-1} a_{n/p} \right) q^n,$$

where $a_{n/p} = 0$ if $p \nmid n$. For $e \geq 2$, let $T_{p^e} = T_p T_{p^{e-1}} - p^{k-1} T_{p^{e-2}}$.

For prime divisors p of N , let the operator U_p satisfy

$$U_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} a_{pn} q^n,$$

and set $U_{p^e} = U_p^e$ where the exponent on the right side means repeated composition. For $n = \prod_p p^{e_p}$, let $T_n = \prod_{p \nmid N} T_{p^{e_p}} \cdot \prod_{p|N} U_{p^{e_p}}$. A *newform* in $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ is a cusp form $f \in S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with $a_1(f) = 1$ that is a simultaneous eigenvector for all Hecke operators T_p for $p \nmid N$ and for all U_p such that $p | N$.

We consider a separate linear map to extract rational expansions from the newforms. For v in a vector space V and a linear map $\mu : V \rightarrow V$, let $\text{tr}(\mu)$ be sum of the eigenvalues of μ . For a finite extension of fields L/K viewed as a vector space over K , let $\mu_\alpha(v) = \alpha v$. We write $\text{Tr}_{L/K}(\alpha) = \text{tr}(\mu_\alpha)$ and consider a finite extension E/\mathbb{Q} such that all of the Fourier coefficients in the expansion of a newform f lie in E . E/\mathbb{Q} is separable, so we may write $E = \mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ for some α in E by the Primitive Element Theorem. It is well known that $\text{Tr}_{E/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha)$ is rational.⁸

In our first example, we inspected the unique-up-to-conjugacy newform f in $S_4(\Gamma_0(11))$, whose coefficient field is $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ with $\alpha^2 - 2\alpha - 2 = 0$ (so $\alpha = 1 \pm \sqrt{3}$). The space has dimension 2 and a single orbit under μ_α of degree 2. We carried out our usual procedures for the sequences $h_n = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_n(f))$ and $h_n^* = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_{pn}(f))$, setting $h_0 = h_0^* = 1$

⁸For example, combine [Orr] (Lemma 19) and [Marcus] (corollary to Theorem 4').

to conform to the hypotheses of equation (D). The minimum-modulus eigenvalue plots for our J matrices are shown in Figure 42. In this example the function $n \mapsto h_n$ is not multiplicative on positive n , and this was the first such example we found with oscillatory behavior.

7. OTHER SEQUENCES

We do not know when oscillations among the minimum moduli occur in the figures below. We have searched unsuccessfully for deciding criteria among the characteristics of modular forms. Now we are looking for such criteria among the characteristic polynomials. We are guessing that such criteria, if there are any, will be easier to spot for sequences h that are constructed as simply as possible. As a beginning, in Figures 48A we display the deformations with $c = 1$ of a minimum modulus plot for the sequence $\{p_{n+1} - p_n - 2\}_{n \geq 1}$. In Figure 48B, we show the corresponding plot for the sequence $\{h_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ with $h_0 = 1$ and $h_n = 2$ for $n \geq 1$. In Figure 48C, we show the corresponding plot for $\{p_{n+1} - p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$. In Figure 49, again deformed with $c = 1$, we depict minimum modulus plots for $\{n^a\}_{n \geq 1}$, $1 \leq a \leq 4$.

The reader will notice, in Fig. 48B, the nearly uniform heights of the μ_n when n is even and their apparently constant value zero when it is odd. We asked Claude to help identify the limit (if it existed) of the even sequence of μ_n 's. It quickly deprived us of the pleasure (which of course we might never have experienced anyway) of solving this riddle by volunteering an analysis using the fact that our (really, López-Bonilla's) Theorem 2.3 simplifies on constant sequences: the heights of the even sequence are converging on the value $1.86209588911\dots = \sqrt{\pi^2/4 + 1}$, and the heights of the odd sequence really are exactly zero. We have a screen shot of the conversation in our depository [Bre25] under the file name "Claude solves $h = 2$ w $c = 1$ ".

Our motive for examining the 2 -sequence was to check (in this example, at least) that constant sequences and their deformed relatives belong to V_h . If not, additive closure of V_h would have failed in this instance.

8. TESTS OF ADDITIVE CLOSURE

Tests of additive closure for V_f are illustrated in Figure 50. We keep track of ongoing tests of V_f closure in Table 2 and of V_h closure in Table 3. (In the code for columns of Table 2 labeled "Plot 1" and "Plot 2", unlike the column "Sum plot", there is no need to take an extra step to extract the list of polynomials. It is just the list of characteristic polynomials.)

We now describe the work flows in the code that produced the tables. Let $E(f_n)$ be the set of zeros of a polynomial f_n and let $\mu_n = \min_{v \in E(f_n)} |v|$. The code for each plot among our figures takes as input a numerical sequence $\{h_n\}$, associates to it a sequence of characteristic polynomials $\{\chi_n\}_n$ in accordance with our lemmas, and creates a list of pairs $\{(n, \mu_n)\}_n$. Finally, the list of pairs is graphed. So the work flow for a given n to generate the

original figures may be sketched as follows:

$$h_n \longrightarrow \chi_n \longrightarrow E(\chi_n) \longrightarrow \mu_n.$$

The code collects the sequences $\{\chi_n\}_n$ and $\{\chi'_n\}_n$ from earlier code that generated plots displaying oscillatory behavior in two of the figures as certified by our Fourier analyses. Because those two plots showed oscillatory behavior, $\{\chi_n\}_n$ and $\{\chi'_n\}_n$ are f -coherent by definition; this is their crucial property for Table 2. The process recorded in Table 2 tests whether or not their sum $\{\chi_n + \chi'_n\}_n$ which is not necessarily a sequence of characteristic polynomials at all, is also f -coherent. If it is, we are looking at an instance of V_f additive closure. The point of compiling Table 2 is to find out whether not we will always see additive closure in these circumstances. Any instance where we do not would refute the hypothesis that V_f is closed under addition.

The code for Table 3 collects h -coherent sequences $\{h_n\}$ and $\{h'_n\}$ from earlier code that generated plots displaying oscillatory behavior in two of our figures, as certified by our Fourier analyses. It forms a third sequence $\{h_n + h'_n\} =$ (say) $\{h''_n\}$, does the workflow

$h''_n \longrightarrow \chi_n \longrightarrow E(\chi_n) \longrightarrow \mu_n$, plots the pairs (n, μ_n) , and tests that set of pairs for oscillatory behavior using Claude’s methods. In other words, the code tests whether or not $\{h''_n\}$ is h -coherent. The summand sequences $\{h_n\}$ and $\{h'_n\}$ are actually modified before we add them to form the sequence $\{h''_n\}$: we abuse our notation and set $h_0 = h'_0 = 1/2$, so that $h''_0 = 1$ in conformance with the hypotheses of our lemmas.

9. TABLES

Supporting data is in SageMath notebooks listed in the index of tables after the bibliography.

1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

TABLE 1. Residues modulo 4 of abscissas from the lower envelope of Figure 2. See notebook `tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25` in [Bre25].

Row	Plot 1	Plot 2	Sum plot
1	Fig. 2B	Fig. 48B	Fig. 50A
2	Fig. 16C	Fig. 17A	Fig. 50B
3	Fig. 2B	Fig. 8C	Fig. 50C
4	Fig. 18B	Fig. 18C	Fig. 50D

TABLE 2. Successful tests for additive closure of V_f . No counterexamples have been detected so far.

Row	Plot 1	Plot 2	Sum plot
1	Fig. 2B	Fig. 48B	Fig. 51A
2	Fig. 16C	Fig. 17A	Fig. 51B
3	Fig. 48A	Fig. 48B	Fig. 48C

TABLE 3. Successful tests for additive closure of V_h . No counterexamples have been detected so far.

10. FIGURES

Supporting data is in SageMath notebooks listed in the index of figures after the bibliography.

FIGURE 1. Minimum moduli for $h_n = \tau(n)$ with $c = 0$.

(A) Matrix method.

(B) Theorem 2.3 method.

FIGURE 2. $c = 1, h_n = \lambda_n$

MINIMUM MODULI

LOGS MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 3. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h_n = \lambda_n$ with $c = 2$.

MINIMUM MÓDULI

LOGS MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 4. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h_n = \lambda_n$ with $c = 3$.

FIGURE 5. Minimum moduli over many values of c for $h_n = \lambda_n$.

FIGURE 6. Minimum moduli for $h_n = \tau(p_n + 1)$ with $c = 1$.

MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 7. Minimum moduli for $h_n = \lambda_n$ before deformation.

FIGURE 8. Cremona curve 11a1.

FIGURE 9. Cremona curve 14a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 10. Cremona curve 15a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 11. Cremona curve 17a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h_n = a(n)$.

(B) $h_n = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h_n = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 12. Cremona curve 19a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 13. Cremona curve 20a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 14. Cremona curve 21a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 15. Cremona curve 24a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 16. Cremona curve 26a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 17. Cremona curve 26b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 18. Cremona curve 27a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 19. Cremona curve 30a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 20. Cremona curve 32a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 21. Cremona curve 33a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 22. Cremona curve 34a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 23. Cremona curve 35a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 24. Cremona curve 36a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 25. Cremona curve 37a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 26. Cremona curve 37b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 27. Cremona curve 38a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 28. Cremona curve 38b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 29. Cremona curve 39a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h_n = a(n)$.

(B) $h_n = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h_n = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 30. Cremona curve 40a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 31. Cremona curve 42a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 32. Cremona curve 43a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 33. Cremona curve 44a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 34. Cremona curve 45a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 35. Cremona curve 46a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 36. Cremona curve 48a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 37. Cremona curve 49a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h_n = a(n)$.

(B) $h_n = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h_n = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 38. Cremona curve 50a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 39. Cremona curve 50b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 40. Cremona curve 51a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 41. Cremona curve 53a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 42. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 1, weight 16.

FIGURE 43. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 4.

FIGURE 44. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 6.

FIGURE 45. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 4.

FIGURE 46. Sum over the first of two Galois orbits with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 6.

FIGURE 47. Sum over the second of two Galois orbits with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 6.

FIGURE 48. Simple h sequences with $c = 1$. An example of additive closure for V_h .

FIGURE 49. $h_n = n^a$, $1 \leq a \leq 4$ with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 50. V_f additive closure tests (sums of V_f polynomials occurring as characteristic polynomials in the named figures) from Column 3 (“Sum plot”) of Table 2.

FIGURE 51. V_h additive closure tests (sums of V_h polynomials occurring as characteristic polynomials in the figures named in the subscripts) from Column 3 (“Sum plot”) of Table 3.

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11. APPENDIX 1: INDEX OF FIGURES

The notebooks are in our repository [Bre25].

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Figure	Notebook
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Figure 43C	N=5, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 3april26

Figure	Notebook
Figure 44A	N=5, k=6 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(n)$ 10april26
Figure 44B	N=5, k=6 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 10april26
Figure 44C	N=5, k=6 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 11april26
Figure 45A	N=11, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(n)$ 12april26
Figure 45B	N=11, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 15april26
Figure 45C	N=11, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 30mar26
Figure 46A	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[0] $h(n) = a(n)$ 12april26
Figure 46B	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[0] $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14april26
Figure 46C	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[0] $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 14april26
Figure 47A	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[1] $h(n) = a(n)$ 15april26
Figure 47B	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[1] $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 16april26
Figure 47C	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[1] $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16april26
Figure 48A	Fig. 48A 30may26
Figure 48B	$h_n = 2$ all n $c = 1$ 3jun26
Figure 48C	Fig. 48C 3jun26
Figure 49A	charpol tests $h(n) = n$ 21may26
Figure 49B	charpol tests $h(n) = n^2$ 20may26
Figure 49C	charpol tests $h(n) = n^3$ 21may26
Figure 49D	charpol tests $h(n) = n^4$ 22may26
Figure 50A	Fig 50A 4jun26
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